

WP2 Conceptualization and System
Architecture

D2.2 Pilot Cases Planning, Scenarios
Definition, Validation Plan

ENIGMA: Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and
provenance management of cultural heritage

ENIGMA CONSORTIUM

<p>Eratosthenes Centre of Excellence (ECoE), Cyprus</p>		
<p>ROYAL MUSEUMS OF ART AND HISTORY KONINKLIJKE MUSEA VOOR KUNST EN GESCHIEDENIS MUSÉES ROYAUX D'ART ET D'HISTOIRE Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis (KMKG), Belgium</p>		
<p>Heritage Malta (HM), Malta</p>		
<p>Miralab Sarl (Mlab), Switzerland</p>		

Project title	Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and provenance management of cultural heritage
Project acronym	ENIGMA
Starting date	01.01.2023
End date	31.12.2025
Contract no.	101094237
Project Coordinator	Charalampos Georgiadis, AUTH, harrisg@civil.auth.gr
Deliverable no.	D2.2
Document name	ENIGMA_D2.2.pdf
Deliverable name	D2.2 Pilot cases planning, scenarios definition, validation plan
Work Package	WP2
Nature ¹	R
Dissemination ²	PU
Lead Beneficiary	10 (NOE)
Contributing beneficiary / beneficiaries	All
Reviewed by	1 (AUTH), 2 (KIKLO)
Approved by	1 (AUTH)
Due date	31/12/2023
Actual submission date	31/03/2025

¹ **R** = Document, Report, **DMP** = Data Management Plan, **OTHER** = Other

² **PU** = Public, **SEN** = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Contents

ENIGMA Consortium.....	2
List of figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	6
Abbreviations	8
Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction.....	10
2. Pilot Cases and related Tools to be implemented & validated.....	11
2.1 Pilot Case 1: Novel Documentation of Museum Items.....	12
2.2 Pilot Case 2: Identification and Tracing of Unregistered CGs.....	12
2.3 Pilot Case 3: Monitoring of Endangered Heritage Sites.....	13
2.4 Pilot Case 4: Validation of the ENIGMA Decision-Support and Data-Communication Platform.....	14
3. Stakeholders' operational scenarios & pilot validation methodology.....	16
3.1 Pilot Case 1 Novel documentation of museum items (HM, KMKG)	17
3.1.1 Data-Entry.....	18
3.1.2 Data Retrieval	20
3.2 Pilot Case 2: Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG, HM)	20
3.2.1 User-1	21
3.2.2 User-2.....	22
3.2.3 User-3.....	22
3.3 Pilot case 3: Monitoring of Endangered heritage (ECoE, KEMEA, HPOL, HM, KMKG).....	25
3.4 Pilot case 4: Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA, HPOL, KMKG, HM & all partners).....	28
3.4.1 LEAs Scenario	30
3.4.2 KMKG Scenario	33
3.4.3 HM Scenario	35
3.5 Overall Pilot Validation Methodology.....	37
3.5.1 Actors envisaged for ENIGMA tools and platform validation.....	37
3.5.2 Overall scope and methodological approach in Pilot Cases' Validation ..	37
3.5.3 Pilot-specific methodologies.....	39
4. Pilot Implementation and Validation Planning	39
4.1 Implementation and Validation Method	42
4.2 Implementation and Validation Planning	42
4.3 Timeline and coordination of Pilot Cases' Implementation and Validation (I+V)	43
4.4 Risk Management.....	44
4.5 List of KPIs	45
5. Platform/Tools Evaluation – Reference Questionnaires	46
5.1 Questionnaire Design	46
5.2 Additional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).....	46
5.3 Preliminary ENIGMA project Questionnaire	47
5.4 Scoring	49

6. Conclusions	49
References.....	51
Annex I: D2.2 ENIGMA Cumulative Overview Table of Pilot Cases' Scenarios & Workflows, Implementation & Validation Planning.....	52
Annex II: Figurines and Objects replicas for Pilot case 2 and 4	55
Annex III: KMKG's current registration and documentation procedures	61

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Pilot case 1 workflow	19
Figure 2: Pilot case 2 workflow	24
Figure 3: Pilot case 3 workflow	26
Figure 4 Schematic representation of the workflow	27
Figure 5 Diagrams depicting the workflow of CG identification and escalation procedures using ENIGMA Platform tools.	30
Figure 6: Pilot case 4 workflow	33
Figure 7: ENIGMA's early technical reference architecture (D2.1)	41
Figure 8: V-model methodology for system development, verification and validation	42
Figure 9 MuseumPlus record: E.432 Lamp (lighting device)	63
Figure 10 MuseumPlus record: E.08670 Vessel(container) Egyptian	64

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Pilot Cases, related Tools, Tasks & Deliverables	11
Table 2: Stakeholders' Operational Scenarios/Workflows & Validation Methodology	16
Table 3: Pilot case 1 scenarios	17
Table 4: Pilot case 1 validation steps	18
Table 5: Pilot case 2 scenarios	20
Table 6: Pilot case 2 validation steps	22
Table 7: Pilot case 3 scenarios	25
Table 8: Pilot case 3 validation steps	25
Table 9 Data table showcasing steps of the CG Identification and Escalation.	28
Table 10: Pilot case 4 scenarios	29
Table 11 Data tables showcasing processed CG information, and coordination actions within the ENIGMA Platform	30
Table 12: Pilot case 4 validation steps	31

Table 13: KMKG Pilot Objects (relevant to Pilot Cases 1, 2, and 4).....	34
Table 14: HM Pilot Objects (relevant to Pilot Cases 1, 2, and 4)	36
Table 15: ENIGMA Target Actors	37
Table 16: General Scope and methodological approach in Pilot Cases' validation ..	37
Table 17: Pilot Implementation and Validation Planning	40
Table 18: Timeline of Pilot Cases' implementation and Validation	43
Table 19: Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures	44
Table 20: Pilot Relevant and Validation KPIs	45
Table 21: ENIGMA– Generic Questionnaire for Effectiveness, Efficiency, Satisfaction & Ease of Use	47

ABBREVIATIONS

Term	Explanation
AAT	Art & Architecture Thesaurus
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Aoi	Areas of Interest
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
CGs	Cultural Goods
CH	Cultural Heritage
CHDS	Cultural Heritage Data
CMS	Collection Management System
DAM	Digital Asset Management
DL	Deep Learning
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EDM	Entity Data Model
EO	Earth Observation
GA	Grant Agreement
HFRG	Human Factors Research Group
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ISO	International Standardization Organization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEA	Law Enforcement Agencies
ML	Machine Learning
MR	Mixed Reality
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SCH	Malta's National Heritage Authority
SDLC	Software Development Life Cycle
TGN	Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names
UAI	Unique Authenticity Identifier
UI	User Interface
UX	User eXperience
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of deliverable D2.2: Pilot Cases Planning, Scenarios Definition, Validation Plan, is to provide a detailed plan for each pilot case, the refinement of scenarios, key functionality of tools to be implemented, as well as the pilot validation framework. This document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement (GA). Therefore, the presentation of the content is divided into the following chapters:

- *Introduction.*
- *Pilot Cases & Tools to be validated*, describing each pilot study along with the related tools which will be used.
- *Pilot Operational Scenarios and Validation Methodology* describing the operational scenarios and workflows for each pilot case and the tools' validation methodology and related steps.
- *Implementation and Validation Planning* describing the planning of implementation and validation for each pilot case.
- *Platform/Tools Validation – Reference Questionnaires*, which provides reference questionnaires' templates for evaluating the platform and tools against specific system features such as efficiency/relevance, effectiveness/utility and satisfaction/clarity.
- *Conclusions*, where there is a summary of the expected outcomes and utilization of this deliverable.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current deliverable presents all pilot cases that will be executed during the ENIGMA project's lifetime, as well as all tools that each pilot will undertake to implement, demonstrate and validate through its proposed operational scenarios. In addition, a plan to outline the technology evaluation method to be used will be produced. The actions taken in the context of WP2 "Conceptualization and System Architecture" are closely connected to the planning, scenario definition and validation of the proposed pilots which are going to be implemented in WP6 "Pilot Cases Implementation, Tools Demonstration and Validation." In this deliverable the objectives are to describe the pilot's plan, initiate the refinement of scenarios, as well as the pilot evaluation framework.

This document can be utilized as an ongoing reference for pilot cases implementation, demonstration and validation. It includes the plan for all pilot cases, their proposed operational scenario & workflow definition, as well as their evaluation and validation framework. The work associated with this deliverable, although is in direct connection the with execution of tasks T6.1 "Pilot implementation, tools demonstration and validation" and T6.2 "Overall system validation" of WP6 "Pilot Cases Implementation, Tools Demonstration and Validation," it will also be closely associated with tools development, integration and pilot implementation from all tasks in WP3 "Technologies of digital identification and tracking of Cultural Goods," WP4 "Technologies for decision-support and public engagement," and WP5 "Integration & Testing," especially in connection to the implementation and evaluation methodology suggested in this deliverable. Given the multitude of ENIGMA pilot cases, the tools to be implemented and validated per pilot case, as well as the associated stakeholders, technology developers and KPIs to be fulfilled, the main chapters of this deliverable begin with an overview table, which summarizes the main information categories that will be further detailed in each chapter. The sum of all these tables has then been assembled and presented as an extensive and concise overview table (depicted in Annex I: D2.2 ENIGMA Cumulative Overview Table of Pilot Cases' Scenarios & Workflows, Implementation & Validation Planning) of pilot cases' scenario definition, implementation and validation planning. Annex I: D2.2 ENIGMA Cumulative Overview Table of Pilot Cases' Scenarios & Workflows, Implementation & Validation Planning will serve as an "at-a-glance" quick reference guide for pilot cases validation planning and execution.

2. PILOT CASES AND RELATED TOOLS TO BE IMPLEMENTED & VALIDATED

Table 1: Pilot Cases, related Tools, Tasks & Deliverables

Chapter 2 - Pilot Cases and related tools to be implemented & validated				
Pilot Cases (pilot leader)		Tools to be validated (tool/task leader)	Relevant project tasks	Relevant project deliverables
#1	<p>Novel documentation of museum items (HM - Heritage Malta)</p> <p>Pilot case #1 deals with the documentation procedures of CGs and is going to test the efficiency and adaptation of the ENIGMA documentation proposals in the internal procedures of the stakeholders.</p>	a) Data modelling, UAI and Digital Twins (KIKLO), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK).	T3.1, T3.4	D3.1, D3.2, D3.4, D3.5
#2	<p>Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG)</p> <p>Pilot Case #2 focuses on testing and evaluating the search tools for unregistered CGs. Different test cases will be performed based on different CGs documentation info to showcase the advantages of novel documentation proposed in Case #1.</p>	[a] Clustering CGs by exploring contextual relationships (UTU), [b] Exploiting metadata analysis to interlink disparate repositories (CLK), [c] Advanced decision-support (CLK), [d] Scenario Building Engine (NoE), [e] Provenance research tool (AUTH).	T3.3, T3.4, T4.1, T4.2, T4.3	D3.2, D3.5, D4.1, D4.2
#3	<p>Monitoring of Endangered heritage sites (ECoE)</p> <p>Pilot Case #3 will evaluate the Earth Observation toolkit by monitoring specific sites using satellite imagery and provide their efficiency and limitations.</p>	[a] Earth observation toolkit (ECoE), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK).	T3.4, T3.5	D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.6
#4	<p>Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA/HPOL)</p> <p>Pilot Case #4 will evaluate the integrated platform and how the individual components work together.</p>	[a] Integration & testing of modules (AUTH), [b] ENIGMA Decision-Support Platform and Data/Communication Platform (CLK), [c] Public engagement tool (KMKG).	T5.1, T5.2, T 5.3	D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5, D5.6

ENIGMA pilot cases (Table 1) aim at providing practical evidence that the developed tools are leading to enhanced preventive methods/technologies and provenance research, while evaluating their efficacy. They will be conducted by a highly qualified multi-disciplinary team comprising CH professionals, archaeologists, museologists, LEAs, computer scientists, engineers, and software developers. The case studies are summarized below, including their objectives, brief description, validation, relevant KPIs and partners involved. During the pilot cases' implementation and validation activities, which will primarily take place within WP6 "Pilot Cases Implementation,

Tools Demonstration and Validation,” the ENIGMA decision-support prototype platform will be evaluated under real conditions including joint collaboration and operations of the partners. Apart from familiarizing practitioners with ENIGMA technologies, the pilots will also serve for the fine-tuning of various methodologies, tools and technologies, that have been developed in previous WPs. Monitoring and risk assessment of CH sites, digital twins for enhanced authentication, decision making, and the adoption of preventive measures are some of the areas that will be tested and evaluated during the pilot studies. The CH items, operational scenarios and workflows, in addition to other complementary data required in pilots belong to the project’s end-user partners and they will be provided by them. The ENIGMA prototype tools, along with their relevant key functionality to be tested and validated, will be provided by the technology providing partners, who will support these pilot implementation and validation cases.

2.1 Pilot Case 1: Novel Documentation of Museum Items

Objective: The main objective of this pilot study is to investigate methods to enhance Authenticity and Traceability of museum items, by introducing and validating novel ways to documentation. It has been noted that the investigation is currently based on a minimum amount of information about the CGs, which puts barriers on tracing them. ENIGMA introduces the concept of Unique Authenticity Identifier (UAI), which introduces protocols on the type and amount of data required for proper authentication that can be scaled across diverse cultural contexts. Pilot Case 1 will validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow. It will also evaluate the application of different practices/strategies according to each host’s regulations and procedures.

Brief Description: Since the most dominant cases of smuggled objects in Europe and worldwide are small items, museum items offer a typical sample of the most important cases to be tested under the ENIGMA activities. Our partners from the end-user communities will test, validate, and evaluate our novel concepts by documenting several of their items using the proposed techniques. These items will be chosen to cover the widest possible range of 2D/3D types, dimensions, physical/material/structural peculiarities and complexities as well as data formats and metadata. The latter will also be used to validate the portability of the information across the current databases/inventories.

Validation: All the pilots will follow the validation plan described in validation steps in section 3.1.1. The results will be validated through KPI2.1-KPI2.7. Through this pilot, the following tools will be validated: [a] Data modelling, UAI and Digital Twins, [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (T3.1, T3.3, T3.4) (D3.1, D3.2, D3.4, D3.5).

Relevant KPIs: KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 (Table 20).

Partners involved: Partners KMKG and HM will apply the developed procedures in their premises, using CH items of their museums. Technical partners (AUTH, ECoE, MLab, UTU, KIKLO, NOE, ASOL) will provide the necessary support and facilitate feedback loops to iteratively refine the procedures based on practical experiences.

2.2 Pilot Case 2: Identification and Tracing of Unregistered CGs

Objective: A major barrier in identification of CGs is that the available technologies presuppose that the CG is known, documented and registered. However, the typical

case in looting and smuggling is that the items are undocumented. ENIGMA tackles the issue by using AI techniques to uncover possible connections of an unknown seized CG to known inventoried objects or heritage sites. The main objective of Pilot Case 2 is to validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow by using scenario building and real museum items (as those documented in Pilot Case 1). It will also evaluate the application of different practices/strategies, taking into account the ethical considerations associated with each host's regulations and procedures.

Brief Description: Partners from the end-user communities will provide test cases from the output of Pilot 1, according to a scenario building scheme (T4.2). These will be followed by metadata from external repositories, regarding known inventoried objects of heritage sites under investigation. The identification of unregistered CGs will be achieved by exploring contextual relations of CG annotations and the developed methods and tools for navigating through connection graphs. The validation of integrity will be checked against known museum items.

Validation: All the pilots will follow the validation plan described in validation steps in section 3.2.3. The results will be validated through KPI2.1-KPI2.7. Through this pilot, the following tools will be validated: [a] Clustering CGs by exploring contextual relationships, [b] Exploiting metadata analysis to interlink disparate repositories, [c] Advanced decision-support, [d] Scenario Building Engine, [e] Provenance research tool (T3.3, T3.4, T4.1, T4.2, T4.3) (D3.2, D3.5, D4.1, D4.2). The performance and the effectiveness of every tool will be measured using a certain number of already known provenance replica objects against system results.

Relevant KPIs: KPI1.3, KPI1.6, KPI1.10, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI2.5, KPI1.7, KPI1.9, KPI1.12, KPI1.18, KPI2.5 (Table 20).

Partners involved: Partners KMKG and HM will provide the test cases (output from Pilot Case 1). A number of them will be used for training and others for validating. In addition, metadata from third parties' repositories will be used. Technical partners (AUTH, MLab, KIKLO, UTU, CLK, KEMEA, ASOL) will process and validate the developed tools.

2.3 Pilot Case 3: Monitoring of Endangered Heritage Sites

Objective: In many cases, smuggling and illicit trading of CGs originate in conflict areas, by looting or deliberate demolition of heritage sites by illegal excavators, or simply through neglect. Thus, besides the damage made to World Cultural Heritage, illicit traffic of CGs and fake provenance are anticipated to appear on the market after such events, not to mention the important fact that most of these items will be unknown and unregistered, making their identification and tracking extremely difficult. Therefore, it is very important to monitor such endangered areas, to detect land changes and alert authorities. The main objective of this pilot study is to validate the developed Earth observation toolkit and the innovative AI techniques as well as the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow. Other important parameters, like big data processing, timely monitoring and alert, fusion of various data sources, detection accuracy and robustness will also be evaluated.

Brief Description: In case of conflict or suspected destruction, Areas of Interest (Aols) are marked and systematically monitored. Optical satellite imagery, SAR images and ground-based data will be preprocessed, harmonized and fused to derive meaningful results related to unexpected land changes. ML-based techniques for satellite image

analysis and change detection are applied and the system automatically triggers alarms when predefined thresholds are exceeded. This scenario will be applied to both known illegal excavations (to validate the ENIGMA toolkits) as well as to other suspected heritage sites. The output will consist of alerts, to highlight potential illegal excavations related to the CG related places.

Validation: All the pilots will follow the validation plan described in validation steps in section 3.3. The results will be validated through KPI2.1-KPI2.7. Through this pilot, the following tools will be validated: [a] Earth observation toolkit, [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (T3.4, T3.5) (D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5). The performance and the effectiveness of EO tool will be measured using a certain number of already known excavation areas against system results in Greece and in Cyprus.

Relevant KPIs: KPI1.14, KPI1.15, KPI1.16 (Table 20).

Partners involved: AUTH, ECoE, UTU, NOE, ASOL and KIKLO will run the pilot, as they are the ones with expertise in Remote Sensing. End-users and LEAs (KMKG, HM, KEMEA, HPOL) will support on site and with item identification.

In order to overcome the issue arising from smuggling and illicit trade of CGs, this pilot study will validate the developed Earth Observation toolkit and the innovative AI techniques.

2.4 Pilot Case 4: Validation of the ENIGMA Decision-Support and Data-Communication Platform.

Objective: The whole suite of developed tools and procedures will finally be integrated into the ENIGMA Decision- support platform (T5.2), which includes: (1) a Decision-Support System, (2) a Communication Platform, and (3) an Advanced data management system. It will also provide a public engagement free API and training material. Therefore, the main objective of this pilot study is to provide an overall assessment of the developed system as well as a validation of the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed integrated workflow. It will also evaluate the application of different practices/strategies according to each host's regulations and procedures.

Brief Description: The output of all previous pilots will be integrated, and multiple scenarios will be processed.

Validation: All the pilots will follow the validation plan described in validation steps in &3.4. The results will be validated through KPI2.1-KPI2.7. Through this pilot, the following tools will be validated: [a] Integration & testing of modules, [b] ENIGMA Decision-Support Platform and Data/Communication Platform, [c] Public engagement tool (T5.1, T5.2, T5.3) (D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5). The performance and the effectiveness of every tool will be measured using a certain number of objects of already known provenance against system results.

Relevant KPIs: KPI1.2, KPI1.3, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.13, KPI1.14, KPI1.15, KPI1.16, KPI1.17, KPI1.18, KPI1.19, KPI2.5 (Table 20).

Partners involved: All ENIGMA partners will be involved in various parts of this pilot. In this pilot case the outputs of all previous pilot studies will be integrated into the ENIGMA Decision – support platform, and multiple scenarios will be processed.

3. STAKEHOLDERS' OPERATIONAL SCENARIOS & PILOT VALIDATION METHODOLOGY

Table 2: Stakeholders' Operational Scenarios/Workflows & Validation Methodology

Chapter 2 - Pilot Cases and related tools to be implemented & validated		Chapter 3 – Stakeholders/LEAs operational scenarios/workflow & validation methodology			
Pilot Cases		Tools to be validated	STKH - LEAs	Scenarios & Workflows	Validation Methodology
# 1	Novel documentation of museum items (HM). Pilot case #1 deals with the documentation procedures of CGs and is going to test the efficiency and adaptation of the ENIGMA documentation proposals in the internal procedures of the stakeholders. Case #1 is about documenting CGs. Parameters of interest include 3D information, descriptions, images, additional info they have in their documentation database for testing and evaluating novel ways for documentation such as creating 3D models of the objects.	a) Data modelling, UAI and Digital Twins (KIKLO), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK).	KMKG, HM	KMKG Operational Scenario: Entering good (detailed and accurate) CG information within the provenance research tool interface for the retrieval of CH goods from the ENIGMA database. Data Entry, Data Retrieval and Validation process steps to be undertaken and assessed.	Different Actors/End-users envisaged in ENIGMA include CH Stakeholders, LEAs and other actors including various public & private organizations and citizens. The methodological approach will examine and assess the Relevance, Effectiveness and Utility of the ENIGMA mechanisms and indicators among different actors and end-users, by implementing, testing and validating the developed tools and the overall ENIGMA architecture against requirements, needs and technical constraints of target actors, as well as general and pilot specific indicators. Data collection and analysis will include 6-10 interviews with various actors per pilot. Pilot Case #1 & #2 will focus on the CH Stakeholders of the project only, whereas Pilot Case #3 on LEAs and Pilot Case #4 on all ENIGMA partners.
# 2	Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG). Pilot Case #2 focuses on testing and evaluating the search tools for unregistered CGs. Different test cases will be performed based on different CGs documentation info to showcase the advantages of novel documentation proposed in Case #1.	[a] Clustering CGs by exploring contextual relationships (UTU), [b] Exploiting metadata analysis to interlink disparate repositories (CLK), [c] Advanced decision-support (CLK), [d] Scenario Building Engine (NoE), [e] Provenance Research tool (AUTH).	KMKG, HM	KMKG Operational Scenario: A user is confronted with an object. The provenance research tool utilizing the UAI will support the user in identification and provenance determination of the object	
# 3	Monitoring of Endangered heritage sites (ECoE). Pilot Case #3 will evaluate the Earth Observation toolkit by monitoring specific sites using satellite imagery and provide their efficiency and limitations, involving CH Stakeholders and LEAs such as KMKG, HM, KEMEA & HPOL.	[a] Earth observation toolkit (ECoE), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK)	ECoE, KMKG, HM, KEMEA, HPOL	Operational Scenario inputs include Satellite Imagery, Historical Records and registered satellite imagery of CH areas and Intelligence reports on suspected trafficking activities. Workflow overview includes Data collection, Threat Assessment & Alert Generation, Collaboration & Escalation, Investigation & Follow-Up, Investigation & Enforcement and Monitoring & Follow-up.	
# 4	Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA/HPOL). Pilot Case #4 will evaluate the integrated platform and how individual components will work together.	[a] Integration & testing of modules (AUTH), [b] ENIGMA Decision-Support Platform and Data/Communication Platform (CLK), [c] Public engagement tool (KMKG)	KEMEA, HPOL, KMKG, HM & all partners	HM Operational Scenario indicates that the National Heritage authority is alerted about an "authentic" artefact for sale in social media and intending to take the following steps: 1. Investigation, 2. Contacting the Seller, 3. Verification Process, 4. Legal, 5. Public Awareness, 6. Resolution. Operational Scenario pertains to detailed narrative on the integration process of ENIGMA Platform tools and their functionalities for LEA CG identification, Decision-Support, Communication, and Data Management within ENIGMA and description of the Public Engagement Tool.	

All pilot cases scenarios and workflows are defined and streamlined in collaboration with CH entities, LEAs, other stakeholders and end-users. Table 2 provides an overview of the operational scenarios and validation methodology for the four pilot cases.

3.1 Pilot Case 1 Novel documentation of museum items (HM, KMKG)

Description: The main objective of this pilot study is to investigate methods to enhance Authenticity and Traceability of museum items, by introducing and validating novel ways to documentation. It has been noted that the investigation is currently based on the minimum amount of information about the CGs, which puts barriers on tracing them. ENIGMA introduces the concept of Unique Authenticity Identifier (UAI), which introduces protocols on the type and amount of data required for proper authentication. Pilot Case 1 validates the authenticity and traceability of the proposed workflow. It also evaluates the application of different practices/strategies according to each host’s regulations and procedures. HM and KMKG will use information coming from their CMS’s. An overview of the current documentation procedures in the CMS at KMKG can be found in Annex III: KMKG’s current registration and documentation procedures.

User Profiles

For this pilot we identify 3 target profiles:

User 1: LEA officers, Border officers

User 2: Experienced LEA officers, Experienced Border officers

User 3: Archaeologists, Museum experts / curators, Ministry of culture

For each of these profiles, specific interfaces and datasets will be prepared. The functionality and services offered by the interfaces depend on the profile of the user and the situation in which the UAI identifier is created or utilized. These user profiles will be used for both pilot case 1 and pilot case 2. Table 3 provides an overview of the scenarios that are going to be implemented in pilot case 1.

Table 3: Pilot case 1 scenarios

	Place	Users involved	Objects
Scenario 1	KMKG	3 curators (KMKG)	List of KMKG objects
Scenario 2	HM	2 curators (HM)	List of HM objects

KMKG Operational Scenario: “Entering good (detailed and accurate) CG information within the Provenance research tool utilizing the UAI for the retrieval of CH goods in the ENIGMA database.”

The UAI is to be understood as a set of data contributing to the identification and provenance of a cultural good. The UAI is flexible in structure. Information can range from limited (only a few fields) to extensive and detailed. The more information the UAI contains, the more detailed and accurate the identification of the object will be. The UAI is not a specific number or code and should not be confused with persistent identifiers, these are used to ensure the identity of a digital asset in the online environment. This pilot tests the interaction of different end-users’ profiles with the interface, the information it contains and the workflow for retrieval and data-entry. In a series of interactions, entering information into the system and evaluating the overall

results, ENIGMA will establish the optimal balance between the effort of data-entry / acquisition and combined with information from other ENIGMA sources, the effectiveness of the UAI. This pilot will test both data entry and data retrieval. The primary goal of pilot case 1 is to assess the easiness of data acquisition for the optimized documentation of a CG, the acceptance of the acquisition workflow by the stakeholders and the effectiveness of the developed tools.

3.1.1 Data-Entry

User-1: For this pilot, we expect User-1 not to be involved.

Users: For User-2 & User-3, ENIGMA will provide a standard/traditional interface for data entry of alphanumeric data, additional information and accompanying files. In addition, it will provide the infrastructure for the creation of a hierarchy. Internationally known vocabularies such as AAT and TGN and their potential use in the UAI will be examined as well. Table 4 presents the validation steps for pilot case 1, while Figure 1 presents the operational workflow of pilot case 1.

Table 4: Pilot case 1 validation steps

Validation Step	Description	Actors	Tools involved	Validation attributes
1.1	Curator inputs minimal quantity of data fields to trace the probable authenticity of the object	User 3	Provenance/UAI	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Interaction Languages
1.2	Response from the system presented: presentation of all information in the UAI. This can consist of images, maps, documents, videos, and scanned documents. The user can select and prioritize information, cluster, link to other objects, create collections, sub-collections	User 3	Provenance/UAI	Visibility Response time Graphics
1.3	Response from the system presented.	User 3	Provenance/UAI	Visibility Response time Languages

	Object is flagged as legitimate or not			
--	--	--	--	--

Pilot Case 1 – Operational Workflow diagram

Figure 1: Pilot case 1 workflow

The following steps are envisaged during the implementation:

1. Enter digital text information into the Provenance research tool utilizing the application, for detail of the information fields see Annex III: KMKG’s current registration and documentation procedures.
2. Add 2D imaging to the Provenance research tool application.
3. Creation of a CG’s 3D model and insertion in the database.
4. The system will provide a list of similar objects based on the provided CG features.
5. The proposed information will be reviewed by the user, and relevant information or insights will be included to the record. Possibly there is a referral to colleague specialists.
6. The UAI record is established.

3.1.2 Data Retrieval

User-2 & User-3. The type of retrieval described here concerns operation within the interface, for data management purposes, access to standard vocabularies etc. Initial retrieval of the information through selection from lists will result in a presentation of all information in the provenance research tool. The validation of this pilot will assess the aspects with steps and relevant information presented in the validation process within Pilot Case 4 further below.

3.2 Pilot Case 2: Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG, HM)

Description: A major barrier in identification of CGs is that the available technologies presuppose that the CG is known, documented and registered. However, the typical case in looting and smuggling is that the items are undocumented. ENIGMA tackles the issue by using AI techniques to uncover possible connections of an unknown seized CG to known inventoried objects or heritage sites. The main objective of Pilot Case 2 is to validate the efficiency and efficacy of the proposed workflow by using scenario building and real museum items (as those documented in Pilot Case 1). It also evaluates the application of different practices/strategies according to each host’s regulations and procedures.

Since authentic museum objects cannot be sent and transferred to LEA officers, a number of cast objects (as reproductions or fakes) have been created and will be transferred for validation purposes. In Annex II: Figurines and Objects replicas for Pilot case 2 and 4 figurines and objects are described in detail. Table 5 presents the scenarios of pilot case 2.

Table 5: Pilot case 2 scenarios

	Object Case	From Place	Object	Users involved	Case escalated to
Scenario 1	Stolen and declared in a database	Museum (KMKG)	No3 (from KMKG list of objects, flagged as stolen)	LEA officer	-
Scenario 2	Stolen but not declared in a database	Museum (HM)	Period 2, Size 2, type 2, civilization 2 (from HM of	LEA officer	Archaeologist

			objects, NOT flagged as stolen)		
Scenario 3	Looted from an illegal excavation	Area from Pilot case 3	No4 (from KMKG list of objects)	LEA officer	-
Scenario 4	Stolen from a museum in a conflict area		Period 4, Size 4, type 4, civilization 4 (from HM list of objects)	LEA officer	Museum Expert (HM)
Scenario 5	Stolen from a monastery / church		No5 (from KMKG list of objects)	LEA officer	Archaeologist

KMKG Operational Scenario: “A user is confronted with an object. The ENIGMA platform will support the user in identification and provenance determination of the object.”

We assume that, when confronted with a CH object these questions will have to be answered:

Documentation:

1. Is there documentation coming with the object?
2. What does the documentation consist of?
3. Is the documentation complete, covering all aspects needed?
4. Is the documentation reliable?
5. Is it possible to establish the owner of the object?
6. Is it possible to establish the destination of the object?

Object further information:

1. Establish the identity of the object: “what is it?”
2. Establish the provenance of an object “Where does it come from?”
3. Is the object authentic/original?
4. Is the provenance (documentation) reliable?

General Question:

Is this transport legal? (based on oral and written evidence).

3.2.1 User-1

When we focus on the operational scenario User-1 will use the ENIGMA platform utilizing the UAI. We expect that User-1 will be confronted with an object of which little information is available. User-1 also lacks the means and experience to assess the object. User-1 may be able to gather some basic information facts, e.g., dimensions, weight, photography, marks, and some information gained from the object’s accompanist like documents, travel, etc. Documents will be scanned, and other information will be fed into the ENIGMA platform. We expect that since the information will not be sufficiently detailed, User-1 will add images and photographs and scans of the accompanying documents. Furthermore, User-1 will be able to use, evaluate and validate the tools for the 3D modelling of a CG. Based on the information entered the

ENIGMA system will visualize and present all the information retrieved for the specific object.

This should support User-1 to decide the next action:

- Decide that the transport is legal.
- Decide that the information is inadequate, and specialist advice is needed.
- Decide that the transport is illegal, take appropriate actions.

In each of the cases User-1 takes appropriate action and documents the decision in the provenance research interface, which is able to alert the respective counterparts:

- In case 1: the decision, the UAI and all the relevant information is recorded in the ENIGMA platform.
- in case 2: notify a specialist and send all recorded and acquired information during assessment.
- In case 3: Notify authorities and take appropriate legal actions.

3.2.2 User-2

User-2 is able to give a more descriptive impression of the object, being able to assess material, declaration and texture as well. Both User-1 and User-2 may be able to create a 3D digital model of the object on location. These 3D models will not have the refined ultra-high quality and resolution of a digital twin, but they will be medium to high quality and resolution 3D models that are optimal for the task at hand. User-2 does not have a role in decisions on legality of the transport or authenticity of the object. However, User-2 is able to document, refine, and add to the information on the ENIGMA platform (enhancing the information contained in the UAI) and thus increase the knowledge.

3.2.3 User-3

User-3 is the expert, who can identify the object in terms of identity and provenance but wants to verify the authenticity of the object and add to the provenance, relate to identified CG to other objects, and possibly define its location of origin. The expert will evaluate the information and sources presented by the provenance research tool and probably add other sources himself. The validation of this pilot will also assess the aspects presented in section 3.4.2. Table 6 presents the validation steps for pilot case 2 while Figure 2 presents its operational workflow.

Table 6: Pilot case 2 validation steps

Validation Step	Description	Actors	Tools involved	Validation attributes
2.1	LEA officer inputs minimal CG information such as dimensions, weight, photo and any document provided to trace the probable authenticity of the object.	User 1 User 2	Provenance/UAI	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms

	LEA officer is assessing the first results and decides if the transport is legal or not.			Response Time Languages Graphics
2.2	LEA officer decides that more info is required and contacts an expert whilst providing more info such as 3D scans, material etc.	User 1 User 2	Provenance/UAI Crowd sourcing analysis tool	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages Graphics
2.3	An expert inputs additional info to the system related to advanced characteristics of the CG object	User 3		Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages Graphics
2.4	Response from the system presented. Object is flagged legitimate or not	User 3		Level of expertise required for operation Visibility Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages Graphics

Pilot Case 2 - Operational Workflow diagram

Figure 2: Pilot case 2 workflow

3.3 Pilot case 3: Monitoring of Endangered heritage (ECoE, KEMEA, HPOL, HM, KMKG)

Pilot Case 3 mainly evaluates the Earth Observation toolkit by monitoring specific sites using satellite imagery and provides their efficiency and limitations. Insofar LEAs are concerned, the following scenario and workflow inputs have already been identified by KEMEA and will be further validated and possibly revised prior to the start of the Pilot Case #3 initiation. During the pilot, the performance of the EO toolkit in detecting illegal excavation sites, will also be validated. Due to the sensitivity and confidentiality of the topic, the toolkit will first be utilized on authorized excavation sites. In the case of analyses of looted sites, authorization is needed, and if obtained, the data will be handled as sensitive. Table 7 presents the scenarios of pilot case 3.

Table 7: Pilot case 3 scenarios

	Site	Alerts	Area is Monitored	Users involved
Scenario 1	Site 1 (Cyprus)	Present	Yes	Cyprus department of Antiquities
Scenario 2	Site 2 (Greece)	No alerts	No	Border Officer
Scenario 3	Site 3 (Syria)	Not Present	Yes	Relevant Authorities

Note: For Alerts and Area monitored columns see the description column in the Validations Steps (Table 8). The operational workflow or pilot case 3 is presented in Figure 3.

Table 8: Pilot case 3 validation steps

Validation Step	Description	Actors	Tools involved	Validation attributes
3.1	<p>Relevant authorities create polygons to provide information for areas that they want to be checked.</p> <p>Border officers and/or local authorities check for alerted areas.</p> <p>If there are no alerts in the area, check if the specific area is monitored.</p> <p>If the area is not monitored, it creates a polygon and runs on demand the analysis</p>	User 1 User 2 User 3	EO tool	<p>Graphics</p> <p>Level of expertise required for operation</p> <p>Functionality</p> <p>Visibility</p> <p>Complexity/ease of use</p> <p>Accessibility on different platforms</p> <p>Response Time</p> <p>Languages</p>

	If alerts exist in the area proceeds to contact experts			
3.2	Expert proceeds with investigation	User 2	RS Alert Web GIS provision	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages Graphics
3.3	Results are presented to the user			

Pilot Case 3 - Operational Workflow diagram

Figure 3: Pilot case 3 workflow

Scenario Inputs:

- Satellite imagery, monitoring area.
- Historical records and registered satellite imagery of CH areas' databases.

Workflow Overview:

- 1. Data Input & Analysis:**
 - Satellite imagery input to EO Toolkit for analysis and for early and accurate detection of any threat or damage on CH.
 - Platform cross-references data with registered items and historical records.
- 2. Threat Assessment & Alert Generation:**
 - EO Toolkit conducts threat assessment, identifying anomalies and potential illegal excavation patterns.
 - Alerts are generated for LEAs upon detecting potential detection of any threat or damage on CH.
- 3. Collaboration & Escalation:**
 - Secure workspace in the ENIGMA platform facilitates LEA collaboration and coordination.
 - Relevant stakeholders are notified, escalating actions for investigation and enforcement.
- 4. Investigation & Follow-Up:**
 - LEAs initiate investigations leveraging EO Toolkit's analysis and evidence.
 - Continuous monitoring and follow-up actions are conducted to track potentially looted items.

Figure 4 provides a schematic representation of the workflow, while Table 9 presents the step-by-step procedure.

Figure 4 Schematic representation of the workflow

Table 9 Data table showcasing steps of the CG Identification and Escalation.

Pilot Scenario: Law Enforcement Agency (LEA) sensitive are Identification and Escalation Validation		
Step 1	Data Collection	LEAs gather and input data of any suspected CH site into the EO Toolkit utilizing information from various sources, including satellite imagery data, intelligence reports, and databases.
Step 2	Threat Assessment	EO Toolkit performs threat assessment and risk analysis based on identified patterns, anomalies, and historical context, aiding LEAs in assessing the severity of potential illegal excavation sites.
Step 3	Alert Generation	Upon detection of potential illicit excavations, the EO Toolkit triggers alerts, notifying relevant authorities and stakeholders for immediate action.
Step 4	Escalation and Collaboration	EO Toolkit facilitates seamless collaboration among LEAs by providing a secure communication channel and shared workspace for coordinated efforts.
Step 5	Investigation and Enforcement	LEAs initiate investigative procedures and enforcement actions based on validated alerts, leveraging ENIGMA's aggregated data and analysis for evidence and legal proceedings.
Step 6	Monitoring and Follow-Up	Continuous monitoring and follow-up actions are conducted using the EO Toolkit to track the status of suspected data of threat or damage on CH, update databases, and prevent further illicit activities in cultural heritage looting.

3.4 Pilot case 4: Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA, HPOL, KMKG, HM & all partners)

Description: The whole suite of developed tools and procedures will finally be integrated into the ENIGMA Decision support platform (T5.2), which includes: (a) a Decision-Support System, (b) a Communication Platform, and (c) an Advanced data management system. It will also provide a public engagement free API and training material. Therefore, the main objective of this pilot study is to provide an overall assessment of the developed system as well as a validation of the efficiency and efficacy of the integrated proposed workflow. It will also evaluate the application of different practices/strategies according to each host's regulations and procedures.

Pilot case 4 will evaluate the integrated ENIGMA platform and the HM and KMKG scenarios in case they are also suitable to be tested here. We will also need to assess, validate, and evaluate the communication and operation of all the developed tools in an integrated way and identify any gaps.

Since authentic museum objects cannot be sent and transferred to the users, a number of cast objects (as reproductions or fakes) have been created and will be transferred for validation purposes. In Annex II: Figurines and Objects replicas for Pilot case 2 and 4 figurines and objects are described in detail.

Table 10: Pilot case 4 scenarios

	Object Case	From Place	Object	Users involved	Case escalated to
Scenario 1	Stolen and declared in a database	Museum (KMKG)	Period 1, Size 1, type 1, civilization 1 (from KMKG list of objects, flagged as stolen)	LEA officer	-
Scenario 2	Stolen but not declared in a database	Museum (HM)	Period 2, Size 2, type 2, civilization 2 (from HM of objects, NOT flagged as stolen)	Border officer	Archaeologist
Scenario 3	Looted from an illegal dig	Area from Pilot case 3	Period 3, Size 3, type 3, civilization 3 (from KMKG list of objects)	LEA officer	-
Scenario 4	Stolen from a museum in a conflict area		Period 4, Size 4, type 4, civilization 4 (from HM list of objects)	LEA officer	Museum Expert (HM)
Scenario 5	Stolen from a monastery / church		Period 5, Size 5, type 5, civilization 5 (from KMKG list of objects)	LEA officer	Archaeologist
Scenario 6	Legal transferred object	Museum (KMKG)	Period 6, Size 6, type 6, civilization 6 (from KMKG list of objects)	LEA officer	-
Scenario 7	Undocumented object		Period 7, Size 7, type 7, civilization 7 (from HM list of objects)	Border officer	Archaeologist

3.4.1 LEAs Scenario

To the extent LEAs are concerned, the following scenario and workflow have already been identified by KEMEA and will be further validated and possibly revised prior to the start of the Pilot Case 4. Figure 5 presents the workflow overview of pilot case 4, while Table 11 provides a step-by-step breakdown. Table 12 describes the validation steps for pilot case 4, and Figure 6 present the operational workflow of pilot case 4.

Textual Scenario Description:

- Detailed narrative explaining the integration process of ENIGMA Platform tools and their functionalities for LEA CG identification.
- Descriptions of how Decision-Support, Communication, and Data Management Systems within ENIGMA aid in risk assessment, coordination, and data management.
- Description of the Public Engagement Tool's features.

Figure 5 Diagrams depicting the workflow of CG identification and escalation procedures using ENIGMA Platform tools.

Table 11 Data tables showcasing processed CG information, and coordination actions within the ENIGMA Platform.

Pilot Scenario: ENIGMA Decision-Support and Data-Communication Platform Validation		
Step 1	Escalation and Collaboration	ENIGMA Decision-Support and Data/Communication Platform facilitates seamless collaboration among LEAs and other stakeholders by providing a secure communication channel and shared workspace for coordinated efforts
Step 2	Investigation and Enforcement	LEAs initiate investigative procedures and enforcement actions based on validated alerts, leveraging ENIGMA's aggregated data and analysis for evidence and legal proceedings
Step 3	Monitoring and Follow-Up	Continuous monitoring and follow-up actions are conducted using the ENIGMA Decision-Support and Data-Communication Platform to track the status of suspected data of threat or damage on CH, update

		databases, and prevent further illicit activities in cultural heritage trafficking
--	--	--

Table 12: Pilot case 4 validation steps

Step	Description	Actors	Tools involved	Validation attributes
4.1	Case: No documents Border officer inputs minimal data fields to trace the probable authenticity of the object	User 1	Provenance/UAI	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Interaction Languages
4.1.1	Case: document(s) exist The Border officer scans the documents and insert them to the system User escalates the case to an expert	User 1	Provenance/UAI	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages
4.2	The system presents the CG relevant info gathered so far and the user provides additional CG information and documents in detail	User 3	Provenance tool/UAI EO tool RS Alert Web GIS provision Crowd Sourcing Analysis Tool	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages Graphics

4.3	The user decides if CG falls under the CG Law security and alerts authorities or doesn't fall under CG law security and flags the CG as not stolen	User 3	Decision Support System (Assessment of spatial Information, Similar Objects and relevant scores, Additional expert info and indicator selection)	Level of expertise required for operation Functionality Visibility Complexity/ease of use Accessibility on different platforms Response Time Languages
-----	--	--------	--	--

Pilot Case 4 - Operational Workflow diagram

Figure 6: Pilot case 4 workflow

3.4.2 KMKG Scenario

In Pilot Case 4 and if suitable, KMKG will examine aspects that remain difficult to describe for this pilot at this stage of the project. Indicative such aspects are presented under the Validation heading below:

Though it is difficult to develop a validation procedure of a product yet to be developed in detail, below we present a number of aspects that will be addressed during the validation activities in addition to an indicative list of pilot objects:

KMKG Validation Aspects (relevant to Pilot Cases #1, #2 & #4)

Interface:

- Level of expertise required for operation
- Sharing information between colleagues
- Functionality
- Visibility
- Complexity
- Ease of use
- Response time
- Legibility
- Accessibility on different platforms
- Interaction
- Languages
- 3D capture solution
- Workflow to add/produce information
- Interaction from interface with other online resources (technical)
- Graphics
- Connections to stakeholders (LEA, CH)

Information

- Languages of the information
- Interaction from interface with other online resources (operational)
- Correctness of the information
- Completeness of the information
- Quality of the additional information in term
- Is the information trustworthy, can the user assess the trustworthiness of the information? Are sources provided?

The following objects (Table 13) are going to be considered during the validation process:

Table 13: KMKG Pilot Objects (relevant to Pilot Cases 1, 2, and 4)

	ID	No	Title
1	214078	A.1676	Oenochoé
2	214764	A.860	Oenochoé
3	215518	A.26	Vase (pot)
4	215519	A.27	Vase à étrier
5	244289	A.4207	Modèle
6	244984	A.13-1	Hydrie
7	295149	A.1669	Vase à étrier
8	304016	A.1228	Fragment
9	304019	A.1229	Fragment
10	304022	A.1231	Pilon

11	304041	A.1230	Fragment
12	304042	A.1232	Fusaïole
13	304043	A.1233	Fusaïole
14	304044	A.1234	Fusaïole
15	304046	A.1235	Fusaïole
16	304072	A.1236	Perle (bijou)
17	304073	A.1237	Bracelet
18	304074	A.1238	Alabastre
19	304075	A.1239	Bol
20	304076	A.1240	Modèle
21	305049	A.1241	Cruche
22	305051	A.1242	Cruche
23	305053	A.1243	Vase (pot)
24	305054	A.1244	Jarre
25	305064	A.1245	Vase à étrier
26	305072	A.1246	Gobelet
27	305073	A.1247-1	Cratère
28	305074	A.1247-2	Cratère
29	307050	A.1227	Bol
30	308018	A.1248-1	Cratère

3.4.3 HM Scenario

The following is a draft scenario proposed by Heritage Malta (HM), which will be finally revised and updated at the start of T6.1.

HM Operational Scenario: “An item appears on social media claiming to be an authentic artefact and is further put on the marketplace for sale. The National Heritage authority is alerted about this by the media.”

In such a scenario, when the National Heritage Authority (SCH) is alerted about an item claiming to be an authentic artifact on social media and being put up for sale on a marketplace, they would likely take the following steps:

1. *Investigation:* SCH would initiate an investigation into the authenticity of the artifact and its potential historical or cultural significance. They may assign experts or archaeologists to assess the item and determine its origin, age, and value (*what happens if they do not have physical access to this?*).

2. *Contacting the Seller:* The authority would reach out to the seller on the marketplace to gather information about the artifact, such as its provenance, acquisition history, and supporting documentation. They would inquire about the source and legal status of the item.

3. *Verification Process:* The SCH would compare the information provided by the seller with their own research and records. They might consult experts in the relevant field to verify the authenticity and significance of the artifact.

4. *Legal Considerations:* If there are concerns about the legality of the artifact's acquisition or export, the SCH may involve law enforcement agencies and customs officials. They would evaluate whether the item was obtained through legal means and if any laws were violated in its sale or export.

5. *Public Awareness:* While the investigation is ongoing, the SCH would likely inform the public about the situation, emphasizing the need for caution when purchasing cultural artifacts and the importance of preserving the national heritage. They may issue statements, hold press conferences, or utilize social media channels to raise awareness.

6. *Resolution:* Depending on the outcome of the investigation, SCH would take appropriate actions. If the artifact is determined to be authentic and significant, they might negotiate with the seller to acquire it for preservation in a museum or a cultural institution. If the artifact is found to be a fake or its provenance is dubious, they would discourage its sale and alert the public about its inauthenticity.

7. *Legal Actions:* In cases where the sale or possession of the artifact violates national laws or international conventions, the SCH authority may initiate legal proceedings against the seller and collaborate with relevant legal authorities to ensure compliance with the law.

Table 14 presents an initial list of HM's CGs that are going to be used in the pilot cases.

Table 14: HM Pilot Objects (relevant to Pilot Cases 1, 2, and 4)

	Registration number	Title
1	MMM 000118	Model of a Catamaran
2	MMM 000594	Waterspout from the Valletta Fish Market's Neptune Fountain
3	MMM 000745	HMS Illustrious Badge
4	MMM 001246	Model of HMS Upholder (P37)
5	MMM 002670	Chain Shot
6	MMM 003900	Gunner's Quadrant with the Coat-of-Arms of Grand Master Manuel Pinto da Fonseca
7	MMM 004014	H.M.S Penelope Badge
8	MMM 004250	Venetian 12-pounder Sagre
9	MMM 004251	Grandmaster Alof de Wignacourt-period Sagre or Half Culverin
10	MMM 004253	Grandmaster Carafa-period Coursier or Half Cannon
11	MMM 004256	Grandmaster Nicolas Cotoner-period Moyana
12	MMM 004257	Grandmaster Carafa-period Moyana
13	MMM 004461	Fish Hawker Badge no.204
14	MMM 004557	Telescope
15	MMM 004750	Bouncy Ball
16	MMM 004871	Half-hull plating model of a 36-foot Double Chine Steel-Work Launch
17	MMM 004879	Lady Emma Hamilton's Bed
18	MMM 005073	Truncheon with Sling of the Admiralty Constabulary

19	MMM 005106	Figurehead of Gregorio Mirabitor
20	MMM 005114	Mortar Shell
21	MMM 005115	Lady travelling case for hats
22	MMM 005117.3	Tin Bucket with Rake and Spade
23	MMM 005119	Foxxna/ Froxxna
24	MMM 005123.6	Pattern used for outside decorative lighting
25	MMM 005135	Furmatur
26	MMM 005141	Boat Scraper
27	MMM 005155	Shears
28	MMM 005166	12.7mm Breda Aircraft Machine Gun
29	MMM 005167	7.92mm MG 15 Machine Gun

3.5 Overall Pilot Validation Methodology

3.5.1 Actors envisaged for ENIGMA tools and platform validation

Table 15 provides an overview of the target actors in the pilot cases.

Table 15: ENIGMA Target Actors

Actors / End Users	Description
LEAs	Law Enforcement Agencies are an important category of end-users, interested in using several of the ENIGMA Platform's tools, aiming to identify antiquities' provenance and pursue all criminal activities.
Archaeologists, Museum experts, relevant authorities	These actors will use the ENIGMA Platform's tools, and they can also define the monitoring areas.
Public	The public will use the crowd sourcing tool to report potential illegal excavations or looting.

3.5.2 Overall scope and methodological approach in Pilot Cases' Validation

The general scope and methodological approach for the validation of the pilot cases is presented in Table 16.

Table 16: General Scope and methodological approach in Pilot Cases' validation

Scope of Pilot Cases	Effectiveness & Utility, Efficiency & Relevance and Satisfaction from using ENIGMA platform, tools and mechanisms among different actors and end-users.
Approach	Implement, test and validate the developed tools and the overall ENIGMA architecture against requirements, needs and technical

	constraints of target actors, as well as general and pilot specific indicators.
Main subjects of evaluation	User interface, adaptation of workflows, ease of use, satisfaction clarity of the procedures, usefulness, etc.) and how (questionnaires, user perspective, scoring of answers, performance indicators, etc.)
Key data collection/analysis methods	6-10 interviews with various actors per pilot
Target Actors	Pilot Case 1 will mainly focus on Museum Experts, Pilot Case 2 will focus on LEAs, whereas Pilot Case 3 focuses on LEAs (EO toolkit), and Pilot Case 4 on all ENIGMA partners (Integrated Platform).
Efficiency & Relevance: the pilot cases evaluate the efficiency and relevance of the ENIGMA tools, services and indicators under the specific operational scenarios proposed	<p>The specific steps to be undertaken to evaluate the relevance of the ENIGMA platform and services in these pilot cases include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying/mapping existing or new data/frameworks collected for various actors through desk research. - Assessing their coverage, completeness, comparing to what ENIGMA offers/develops. - Conducting an interview programme, which involves a presentation of the ENIGMA tools & services developed on the basis of the results of desk analysis. - Assessing functionality, ease of use, presentation of tools and platform - Testing the proposed set of indicators against the needs of the actors/end-users.
Effectiveness & Utility: the pilot cases evaluate the effectiveness and utility of the ENIGMA tools, set of services and indicators under the specific stakeholders' operational scenarios proposed	<p>By conducting company data analysis, we aim to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Present preliminary findings to various actor groups for whom data is derived in ENIGMA. - Check with interviewees whether the findings match their expectations/perceptions. - Identify outputs which were produced by the project partners. - Check if and how they were linked to project activities. - Compare the findings to the results obtained in ENIGMA. - Explore possible links with other relevant EU-HE projects. - Examine the match between these outputs, identified impacts and their stories.

<p>Satisfaction & Clarity: the pilot cases evaluate the satisfaction and clarity in utilizing the ENIGMA tools and set of services under the specific stakeholders’ operational scenarios proposed</p>	<p>By conducting company data analysis, we aim to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Present preliminary findings to various actor groups for whom data is derived in ENIGMA. - Check with interviewees whether the findings match their expectations/perceptions. - Identify outputs which were produced by the project partners. - Check if and how they were linked to project activities. - Compare the findings to the results obtained in ENIGMA. - Explore possible links with other relevant EU-HE projects. - Examine the match between these outputs, identified impacts and their stories.
---	---

3.5.3 Pilot-specific methodologies

As mentioned in the previous section, each pilot will be structured around the research questions aiming to assess the applicability and practicability of the proposed methods and indicators, in terms of their relevance and effectiveness, as well as utility in the specific settings of the stakeholders and countries. However, each pilot study will also cover a particular theme related to the data and results obtained in ENIGMA. The subsequent sections outline the pilot specific content.

Based on the general scope and methodological approach in pilot cases’ evaluation of Table 16 above, pilot-specific methodologies will be defined, agreed and reviewed during the first months of the Pilot Implementation & Validation preparatory phase in WP6, as indicated in Table 17 in the next chapter. Pilot-specific methodological approach and questionnaires’ templates can utilize the structure of Table 16 and those referred to in chapter 5 as a starting point.

4. PILOT IMPLEMENTATION AND VALIDATION PLANNING

Table 17: Pilot Implementation and Validation Planning

Chapter 2 - Pilot Cases, Tools and Tasks			Chapter 4 - Pilot Implementation and Validation Planning		
Pilot Cases (pilot leader)	Tools to be validated (tool/task leader)	Tasks	Implementation & Validation Planning	Relevant and Validation KPIs	Partners involved
# 1 Novel documentation of museum items (HM - Heritage Malta) Pilot case #1 deals with the documentation procedures of CGs and is going to test the efficiency and adaptation of the ENIGMA documentation proposals in the internal procedures of the stakeholders.	a) Data modelling, UAI and Digital Twins (KIKLO), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK)	T3.1 T3.4	ENIGMA pilots' implementation and validation will be executed during tasks T6.1, T6.2 and partially through T6.3. Task T6.1- Pilot implementation, tools demonstration and validation (M17-M32, Lead: ECoE), focuses on managing and monitoring the execution of the pilot cases and the validation of developed tools. Task T6.2-Overall system validation (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), includes the involvement of experts and various organizations to manage the testing and validation of system's modules and components. Performance metrics will be monitored during the implementation of pilots. Task T6.3-Policy Framework & Recommendations (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), a set of policy recommendations for regional, national and EU policy makers and proposals for improvement and further steps will be developed. There is significant overlapping of task T6.1 with tools' development, integration and testing tasks in WP3, WP4, & WP5, since the task is initiated quite early (M17) in the project, to best serve this particular purpose. This will enable the Agile SDLC implementation and validation methodology to work out properly, especially by implementing and testing small chunks of software code or certain parts of the tool's functionality. The early engagement of the project's stakeholders will ensure the tools' adequate execution, by providing data and feedback (via scientific questionnaire and/or interview-based assessment) regarding the system and its functionalities. Further to the adoption of an Agile System/Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework, ENIGMA will undertake the " V-model" methodological approach for verification and validation. The Agile SDLC model complies with the ISO/IEC. 27001/2, ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015 and ISO/IEC TR 90005:2008 as well as ISO/IEC 12207:2008 and ISO/IEC 90003:2014 international standards.	Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.7	AUTH, ECoE, MLab, UTU, KIKLO, NOE, ASOL
# 2 Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG) Pilot Case #2 focuses on testing and evaluating the search tools for unregistered CGs. Different test cases will be performed based on different CGs documentation info to showcase the advantages of novel documentation proposed in Case #1.	[a] Clustering CGs by exploring contextual relationships (UTU), [b] Exploiting metadata analysis to interlink disparate repositories (CLK), [c] Advanced decision-support (CLK), [d] Scenario Building Engine (NoE), [e] Provenance research tool (AUTH)	T3.3 T3.4 T4.1 T4.2 T4.3		Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.12	AUTH, MLab, KIKLO, UTU, CLK, KEMEA, ASOL
# 3 Monitoring of Endangered heritage sites (ECoE) Pilot Case #3 will evaluate the Earth Observation toolkit by monitoring specific sites using satellite imagery and provide their efficiency and limitations.	[a] Earth observation toolkit (ECoE), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK)	T3.5		Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.13	AUTH, ECoE, UTU, NOE, ASOL and KIKLO
# 4 Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA/HPOL) Pilot Case #4 will evaluate the integrated platform and how the individual components work together.	[a] Integration & testing of modules (AUTH), [b] ENIGMA Decision-Support Platform and Data/Communication Platform (CLK), [c] Public engagement tool (KMKG)	T5.1 T5.2 T5.3		Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.12	All ENIGMA partners

The ENIGMA platform will be composed of a collection of different applications, tools and **set of services** that will be integrated to provide a holistic solution for the protection of CGs, as this is depicted in its initial reference architecture (Figure 7):

Figure 7: ENIGMA's early technical reference architecture (D2.1)

The following **Service Sets** (as these have been depicted in D2.1), along with accompanying tools and applications are going to be developed during the course of the ENIGMA project:

- Service Set #1: Data modelling and digital Twins for enhanced authentication/preservation. Service Set #1 will develop the novel concept of the UAI. It will also develop a fast on-site documentation toolkit.
- Service Set #2: 3D reconstruction technologies. Service set #2 will provide advanced capabilities to address the requirements of highly accurate and efficient identification of un-registered CGs.
- Service Set #3: CGs stratification AI tools. Service set #3 will support the end-users of ENIGMA (i.e., an archaeologist, border guards, researchers) to gain information about a closest object related to the one the end-user is analyzing.
- Service Set #4: Web crawler and data sharing in joint workspace technologies. Service set #4 will be designed to extract metadata, including images and videos from databases for stolen artefacts in real time.
- Service Set #5: EO toolkit. Service set #5 will exploit the capabilities and characteristics of the freely available Copernicus Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite sensors, and other satellite-based services that concentrate on the systematic monitoring of areas of CH interest.
- Service Set #6: Decision support module. Service set #6 will include AI and ML models and algorithms in order to quickly classify and depict desirable features and details with high accuracy.
- Service Set #7: Scenario Building Engine. Service set #7 will support key functionalities for process mapping and modelling of operating workflows & procedures of key stakeholders and LEAs.
- Service Set #8: Comprises different tools / components and utilizes the output of other services developed within ENIGMA in order to determine the provenance of an object.

4.1 Implementation and Validation Method

For its implementation, ENIGMA will adopt an Agile System/Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework, a widely applied and utilised iterative and incremental software development model, while it will undertake the "V-model" methodological approach for verification and validation. The agile SDLC model comply with the ISO/IEC 27001/2, where the term "system" comprises not only software, but also hardware, data, people, processes, procedures, facilities, and materials. ISO (International Organization for Standardization) has standards covering both the system (ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288:2015 and ISO/IEC TR 90005:2008) and software (ISO/IEC 12207:2008 and ISO/IEC 90003:2014) approaches.

Figure 8: V-model methodology for system development, verification and validation

The Agile approach to software/system development is more flexible and open to changes than the older and more rigid Waterfall approach, which makes it more suitable for projects affected by rapid changes. A key difference between the two methodologies is the project's flow. While waterfall is a linear and sequential approach, Agile is an iterative and incremental approach. In practice this means that software created using Agile has development phases we may perform several times with smaller chunks of implemented functionality. The two methodologies also have different approaches to testing. The waterfall methodology tests implementation very late in the process while Agile integrates tests for each iteration. Another key difference is the two methodologies' approach to stakeholders. When we use waterfall, the end-user doesn't see the implemented software until quite late in the project. When we use Agile, end-users have the opportunity to follow the progress along the way. The final integration workflow will be defined in WP5 through the implementation of T5.1 "Integration & testing of modules to support operational procedures."

4.2 Implementation and Validation Planning

ENIGMA pilots' implementation and validation will be executed during tasks T6.1, T6.2 and partially through T6.3. T6.1-Pilot implementation, tools demonstration and validation (M17-M32, Lead: ECoE), which focuses on managing and monitoring the

execution of the pilot cases and the validation of developed tools. During the demonstration phase, technical partners and end-users of the project will be involved to use the system and to report on its benefits, providing data and feedback (via scientific questionnaire and/or interview-based assessment) regarding the system and its functionalities. In addition, T6.2-Overall system validation (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), which includes the involvement of experts and various organizations to manage the testing and validation of system’s modules and components. Performance metrics will be monitored during the implementation of pilots. T6.3-Policy Framework & Recommendations (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), where a set of policy recommendations for regional, national and EU policy makers and proposals for improvement and further steps will be developed. It will take the form of a white paper, which will be elaborated with the participation of a wide spectrum of stakeholders for each country covered by the project, through a fact-based and multi-level stakeholder dialogue. The white paper will provide a basis for policymakers and stakeholders for developing informed policy and for analyzing sector dynamics. The white paper will assess the identified barriers and propose strategies to support and enhance social awareness of CH and more citizen engagement, focusing on a wide spectrum of challenges including socioeconomics, politics, and gender. During this task implementation and through the integration and testing of the public engagement tool in the ENIGMA platform, support to its outcomes can be provided via the public’s engagement with project findings and results.

There is significant overlapping of task T6.1 with the tools’ development, integration, and testing tasks in WP3, WP4, & WP5, since the task is initiated quite early (M17) in the project, to best serve the tools’ early integration in the ENIGMA Platform, as well as their adequate pilot implementation and validation. This will enable the Agile SDLC implementation and validation methodology to work out properly, especially by implementing and testing small chunks of software code or certain parts of the tool’s functionality, with the early engagement of the project’s stakeholders in ensuring the tools’ proper functionality, by providing data and feedback (via scientific questionnaire and/or interview-based assessment) regarding the system and its functionalities.

4.3 Timeline and coordination of Pilot Cases’ Implementation and Validation (I+V)

Table 18: Timeline of Pilot Cases’ implementation and Validation

Pilot Case I+V phases	Sub-task/Activity	Approx. Start/End dates	Deliverables reflecting pilot case phases outcomes
Pilot I+V Preparatory Phase	Present initial tool prototypes and their functionalities to project actors/end-users, collecting initial feedback and comments to streamline final tool development phase (M18-30)	May – June 2024	D3.1, D3.2, D3.3 → M18 D4.1 → M18 D5.2 → M18
	Finalize Stakeholders’ operational scenarios/workflows & pilot-specific methodologies	July - Sept.2024	D5.3 (D5.5) → M24
	Engage with desk research and prepare stakeholders to carry out tools and platform I+V	Oct.- Dec. '24	

Pilot I+V Phase 1	Tools & Platform development finalized & readiness for actual Pilots' I+V	Jan.- June 2025	D3.4, D3.5, D3.6 → M30 D4.2 → M30 D5.4, D5.6 → M30
Pilot I+V Phase 2	Final Pilots' Tools Evaluation & Validation and Policy Brief	June–August 2025	D6.1, D6.3 → M32
Pilot I+V Phase 3	Final Pilots' Platform Evaluation, System Validation and Policy Recommendations	Aug.-December 2025	D6.2, D6.4 → M36

The overall coordination of the individual pilot cases' implementation and validation is important in order to ensure that their progress meets the overall targeted goals, and that results, feedback, and required inputs are provided to technology partners, various stakeholders, deliverable leaders and KPIs in due time and quality.

The Pilot Case leaders are responsible for liaising closely with other task leaders in WP3, WP4, WP5 & WP6 in finalizing the individual pilot methodologies, implementing the pilots in line with objectives and due times. The Pilot Case Leaders are also responsible for delivering regular status updates and input for the WP6 task deliverables. The progress of all pilots will be monitored and briefly reported in regular (time interval to be agreed) coordination calls to consortium partners.

4.4 Risk Management

Table 19: Potential Risks and Mitigation Measures

Description of risk	Risk mitigation measures	Probability	Impact
Low mobilization of stakeholders to proactively participate in and contribute to the WP6 activities	Thanks to previous work of ENIGMA partners in the field of IT tools and platforms implementation in relation to CH stakeholders, strong links and networks have already been established. The established and active networks reduce this risk considerably.	Low	Low
Committed stakeholders involved in the pilot(s) resign from participation	To motivate and bind the stakeholders to the ENIGMA activities, the project team will establish a good communication basis between the project and the stakeholders. The team will strive to respond to the stakeholders' needs, pressing issues, and interests by coordinating and flexibly adapting the pilots in close collaboration with them.	Low	Medium
Evaluation of use case fails to meet the requirements due to poor implementation	To mitigate this risk the consortium will evaluate the relevance, effectiveness and utility of the ENIGMA indicators in specific pilot contexts. The methodological approach of the pilot studies, as well as their individual implementation strategies, will be carefully monitored, assessed, and if necessary revised. By establishing a good communication and collaboration basis with the stakeholders, the ENIGMA team will make sure to align and achieve a common understanding of the pilot goals and methodologies. Beyond that, the ENIGMA team has defined roles and	Low	Low

	tasks for the stakeholders involved as well as the ENIGMA partners.		
Evaluation of pilot case fails to meet the requirements due to missing engagement by selected stakeholder group	To ensure broader participation of stakeholders in the relevant pilot cases we will select them based on their availability, engagement with the project and their openness to adopt new indicators. By closely communicating and coordinating with the stakeholders, the ENIGMA team will strive to motivate and bind the stakeholders to the project activities.	Low	Medium

4.5 List of KPIs

All pilot implementation and validation steps will be finalised and planned in detail prior to the beginning of task T6.1 in close collaboration between T6.1 leader, respective pilot tools leaders and associated pilot partner stakeholders. During the same period the pilot operational scenario/workflow shall also be finally revised, comprising a guide for its implementation and validation and following the respective methodology as described earlier in this deliverable. Where appropriate, KPI metrics will be collected through specific questionnaires or interviews with project partners and external stakeholder, citizens or target groups. The pilot-relevant KPIs are the following:

KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18.

The pilot validation KPIs include KPI2.1 to KPI2.7.

All KPI metrics registration and monitoring throughout WP6 will be the responsibility of the relevant task leaders in close association and support from the pilot case leaders.

Here below (Table 20) is the list of Pilot Relevant and Pilot Validation KPIs with their descriptions and targets set.

Table 20: Pilot Relevant and Validation KPIs

KPI #	Description	Target
Pilot-Relevant KPIs		
1.1	Alignment of user needs to novel technological capabilities	>20%
1.2	Quality and Quantity of collected data for CGs identification	>50%
1.4	Improvement of Object identification and traceability strategy	>40%
1.6	Improvement of Ability to find and process joint cases	>40%
1.7	Number of prototypes/toolkits for enhanced digital CGs identification	>3
1.8	Number of exemplary cases of CGs types	>10
1.9	Number of CG clustering/stratification workflows and tools	>3
1.10	Number of integrity validation cases	>3
1.11	Improvement of Identification of registered CGs	>50%
1.12	Improvement of Identification of un-registered CGs	>50%
1.18	Improvement of Provenance validation	>50%
Pilot Validation KPIs		
2.1	Number of stakeholders taking part in engagement platform	>20
2.2	Number of countries taking part	>5

2.3	Number of persons/general public taking part	>100
2.4	Number of downloads of public API	>50
2.5	Number of pilot cases for validation	4
2.6	Number of Locations of pilots	>3
2.7	Number of participating end-user organizations	>5

5. PLATFORM/TOOLS EVALUATION – REFERENCE QUESTIONNAIRES

This chapter provides a preliminary design of ENIGMA Platform/Tools’ evaluation questionnaires, as references for its Pilots’ evaluation regarding the validation of workflows, procedures and software tools. These include different types of questionnaires, measurement categories, particular questions per category, scoring method & range and specific performance indicators. They will be used for evaluating different system attributes and performance, such as User Interface & User Experience (UI/UX), platform/tools (hardware and software) functionalities, adaptation of workflows, ease of use, clarity of the procedures, usability, usefulness, etc.

5.1 Questionnaire Design

Questionnaires are often regarded as a convenient way to gather data from a large number of participants. A well-designed questionnaire can gather information about the overall performance of a product or system, as well as information on specific components (Ryu, 2005). One of the single greatest advantages of using questionnaires in usability research is that questionnaires can provide evaluators with feedback from the users’ point of view (Annett, 2002; Baber, 2002; Kirakowski, 2003). Since user-centered and participatory design is one of the most important aspects in the usability engineering process (Keinonen, 1998), questionnaires can be an essential method, assuming that the respondents are validated as representative of the whole user population (Ryu, 2005).

Going through a number of such questionnaires, specifically designed to assess aspects of usability, validity and/or reliability of similar to ENIGMA’s platform/tools, we have examined several types of them (Tullis & Albert 2008) and also from similar instruments in Human Factors Research Group (HFRG).

5.2 Additional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The design of the final questionnaire(s) for evaluating the ENIGMA Platform/Tools will be based on those reviewed above, taking into consideration **additional KPIs**, such as:

- **Effectiveness** (as the perceived usefulness and trust for scalability, availability, security and usability), associated also with Utility of project results
- **Efficiency** (as the perceived ease of use and learnability), associated also with Relevance of project results, and finally
- **Satisfaction** (perceived as the user comfort of use and lostness or fatigue when using the system), associated with project results clarity

5.3 Preliminary ENIGMA project Questionnaire

Having reviewed and considered several questionnaire types, we have designed a **preliminary ENIGMA Questionnaire**, also considering relevant questions to be able to better assess the additional KPIs mentioned in the previous paragraph. This can be used as an initial template to finalize those that will be used in the Pilot Cases evaluation.

Table 21: ENIGMA– Generic Questionnaire for Effectiveness, Efficiency, Satisfaction & Ease of Use

<u>ENIGMA – Generic Questionnaire for Effectiveness, Efficiency, Satisfaction & Ease of Use</u>								
Please rate your satisfaction with the system.								
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Try to respond to all the items. • For items that are not applicable, use: NA • Add a comment about an item by clicking on its icon, or add comment fields by clicking on Comment All. 								
		1	2	3	4	5		N/A
EFFICIENCY & RELEVANCE								
Specified data and/or frameworks are evidently complete	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
The user requirements have been properly covered	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Tools/platform functionality is in line with specifications	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Grade your overall usage satisfaction	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Would you recommend it to a friend?	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Would you wish to purchase or have it at some point?	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
EASE OF USE								
It makes things I want to accomplish easier to get done.	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It is easy to use	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
The GUI is adequate for its prescribed use and utility	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It is user-friendly	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It requires the fewest steps possible to get what I want to do with it.	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It is flexible.	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Using it is effortless.	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0

I can use it without written instructions	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I don't notice any inconsistencies as I use it	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Both occasional and regular users would like it	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I can recover from mistakes quickly and easily	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
The overall user experience has been very positive	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I can use it successfully every time	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
EASE OF LEARNING								
Grade the easiness of required initial training	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Grade the length of required training	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I learned to use it quickly	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I really remember how to use it	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It is easy to learn how to use it	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I quickly became skillful with it	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
SATISFACTION & CLARITY								
Grade if system matches your overall expectations/perceptions	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It has been easy to identify outputs which were produced by the project partners	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It was easy to link these outputs to project activities	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
Grade your overall usage satisfaction	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I would recommend it to a friend	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
I wish to purchase it or have it at some point	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0
It is pleasant to use	Strongly disagree	0	0	0	0	0	Strongly agree	0

Validation attributes questionnaire options:

1. **Level of expertise** required for operation

Questionnaire form with options 1: No experience 2: Little experience 3: Expert

2. **Functionality:** How well the system performs in its functional aspects

Questionnaire form with options 1: Bad 2: Good 3: Excellent

3. **Visibility:** Is there any issue in UI in terms of visibility in input fields or any input information

- Questionnaire form with options 1: Bad 2: Good 3: Excellent
4. **Complexity/ease of use**
Questionnaire form with options 1: Bad 2: Good 3: Excellent
 5. **Accessibility** on different platforms: Is the system accessible on any platform
Questionnaire form with options 1: Yes 2: No, please specify in which platform you encountered accessibility issues
 6. **Response Time**: The system has responded fast enough
Questionnaire form with options 1: Slow response 2: Medium response 3: Fast response
 7. **Languages**: The system should include more languages than English alone
Questionnaire form: Please specify additional languages
 8. **Graphics**: The system graphics are clear, self-explained and well designed to transfer the corresponding info to the user
Questionnaire form with options 1: Yes 2: Yes, but need some improvement 3: Should be redesigned

5.4 Scoring

The Likert scale is the one most commonly used in questionnaires for scoring the evaluation. It is based on forced choice questions, where a statement is made, and the respondent then indicates the degree of agreement or disagreement with the statement on a 5 (or 7) point scale (Brooke, 1996). There is a potential problem with the Likert scale from the interpretation of the neutral option, therefore it is advisable that people completing the questionnaire should be advised to avoid that option too often in order to have a clearer picture on their scoring.

Typically, a median threshold score of 3.0 out of 5.0 is broadly considered as satisfactory for pilot systems' evaluation, thus it is proposed to adopt this as our project's minimum success composite metric, subject to be agreed with all consortium partners.

6. CONCLUSIONS

ENIGMA deliverable D2.2 *Pilot cases planning, scenarios definition, validation plan* provides an analytical view and reference material towards fulfilling the project's scientific, technical and contractual objectives through the detailed planning of their pilot cases' implementation, evaluation and validation.

Pilot cases, association to tools, platform, tasks and deliverables have been described, in relation to appropriate stakeholders and LEAs operational scenarios and workflows. The pilot cases evaluation methodology including reference questionnaires for different types of system performance attributes and end-users' aspects, such as UI/UX, user satisfaction, efficiency and effectiveness of use, in addition to measurement and fulfilment of prescribed KPIs have been provided.

D2.2 aspires to comply with and maintain the project's high standards in attaining its ambitious objectives for becoming the EU's flagship project in providing innovative

tools and solutions to all involved stakeholders in fighting against CGs theft and illicit trafficking.

REFERENCES

- [1] Annett, J. (2002). Target paper. Subjective rating scales: Science or art? *Ergonomics*, 45(14), 966-987.
- [2] Baber, C. (2002). Subjective evaluation of usability. *Ergonomics*, 45(14), 1021-1025.
- [3] Brooke, J., 1996, SUS: A "quick and dirty" usability scale. In P. W. Jordan, B. Thomas, B. A. Weerdmeester, & A. L. McClelland (Eds.), *Usability Evaluation in Industry*. London: Taylor and Francis.
- [4] Keinonen, T. (1998). One-dimensional usability - influence of usability on consumers' product preference: University of Art and Design Helsinki, UIAH A21.
- [5] Kirakowski, J. (2003). Questionnaires in usability engineering: A list of frequently asked questions [HTML].
- [6] Ryu, Young Sam, 2005, *Development of Usability Questionnaires for Electronic Mobile Products and Decision Making Methods*, PhD Dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University.
- [7] Tullis, T., Albert, B., 2008, *Measuring the User Experience: Collecting, Analyzing, and Presenting Usability Metrics*, p.317 Morgan Kaufmann Publishers

ANNEX I: D2.2 ENIGMA CUMULATIVE OVERVIEW TABLE OF PILOT CASES' SCENARIOS & WORKFLOWS, IMPLEMENTATION & VALIDATION PLANNING

D2.2 ENIGMA Cumulative Overview Table of Pilot Cases' Scenarios & Workflows, Implementation & Validation Planning

Chapter 2 - Pilot Cases and related tools to be implemented & validated				Chapter 3 - Stakeholders' operational scenarios/workflow & validation methodology			Chapter 4 - Pilot Implementation and Validation Planning			
Pilot Cases		Tools	Tasks	Deliverables	STKH - LEAs	Scenarios & Workflows	Validation Methodology	Implementation & Validation Planning	Relevant and Validation KPIs	Partners involved
#1	<p>Novel documentation of museum items (HM - Heritage Malta) Pilot case #1 deals with the documentation procedures of CGs and is going to test the efficiency and adaptation of the ENIGMA documentation proposals in the internal procedures of the stakeholders.</p>	<p>[a] Data modelling, UAI and Digital Twins (KIKLO), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK)</p>	<p>T3.1, T3.4</p>	<p>D3.1, D3.2, D3.4, D3.5</p>	<p>HM, KMKG</p>	<p>KMKG Operational Scenario: Entering good (detailed and accurate) CG information within the provenance research tool interface for the retrieval of CH goods in the ENIGMA database. Data Entry, Data Retrieval and Validation process steps to be undertaken and assessed.</p>	<p>Different Actors/End-users envisaged in ENIGMA include CH Stakeholders, LEAs and other actors including various public & private organizations and citizens. The methodological approach will examine and assess the Relevance, Effectiveness and Utility of the ENIGMA mechanisms and indicators among different actors and end-users, by implementing, testing</p>	<p>ENIGMA pilots' implementation and validation will be executed during tasks T6.1, T6.2 and partially through T6.3. Task T6.1-Pilot implementation, tools demonstration and validation (M17-M32, Lead: ECoE), focuses on managing and monitoring the execution of the pilot cases and the validation of developed tools. Task T6.2-Overall system validation (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), includes the involvement of experts and various organizations to manage the testing and validation of system's modules and components. Performance metrics will be monitored during the implementation of pilots. Task T6.3-Policy Framework &</p>	<p>Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.7</p>	<p>AUTH, ECoE, MLab, UTU, KIKLO, NOE, ASOL</p>

<p>#2</p>	<p>Identification and tracing of unregistered CGs (KMKG) Pilot Case #2 focuses on testing and evaluating the search tools for unregistered CGs. Different test cases will be performed based on different CGs documentation info to showcase the advantages of novel documentation proposed in Case #1.</p>	<p>[a] Clustering CGs by exploring contextual relationships (UTU), [b] Exploiting metadata analysis to interlink disparate repositories (CLK), [c] Advanced decision-support (CLK), [d] Scenario Building Engine (NoE), [e] Provenance research tool (AUTH)</p>	<p>T3.3, T3.4, T4.1, T4.2, T4.3</p>	<p>D3.2, D3.5, D4.1, D4.2</p>	<p>KMKG, HM</p>	<p>KMKG Operational Scenario: A user is confronted with an object. The provenance research tool utilizing the UAI will support the user in identification and provenance determination of the object</p>	<p>and validating the developed tools and the overall ENIGMA architecture against requirements, needs and technical constraints of target actors, as well as general and pilot specific indicators. Data collection and analysis will include 6-10 interviews with various actors per pilot. Pilot Case #1 & #2 will focus on the CH Stakeholders of the project only, whereas Pilot Case #3 on LEAs and Pilot Case #4 on all ENIGMA partners.</p>	<p>Recommendations (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), a set of policy recommendations for regional, national and EU policy makers and proposals for improvement and further steps will be developed. There is significant overlapping of task T6.1 with tools' development, integration and testing tasks in WP3, WP4, & WP5, since the task is initiated quite early (M17) in the project, to best serve this particular purpose. This will enable the Agile SDLC implementation and validation methodology to work out properly, especially by implementing and testing small chunks of software code or certain parts of the tool's functionality. The early engagement of the project's stakeholders will ensure the tools' adequate execution, by providing data and feedback (via scientific questionnaire and/or interview-based assessment) regarding the system and its functionalities. Further to the adoption of an Agile System/Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework, ENIGMA will undertake the " V-model" methodological approach for verification and validation. The Agile SDLC model complies with the ISO/IEC. 27001/2, ISO/IEC/IEEE</p>	<p>Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.12</p>	<p>AUTH, MLab, KIKLO, UTU, CLK, KEMEA, ASOL</p>
<p>#3</p>	<p>Monitoring of Endangered heritage sites (ECoE) Pilot Case #3 will evaluate the Earth Observation toolkit by monitoring specific sites using satellite imagery and provide their efficiency and limitations.</p>	<p>[a] Earth observation toolkit (ECoE), [b] Data sharing in joint Workspace (CLK)</p>	<p>T3.5</p>	<p>D3.3, D3.6</p>	<p>ECoE, KMKG, HM, KEMEA, HPOL</p>	<p>Operational Scenario inputs include Satellite Imagery CH Data, Historical Records and registered satellite imagery of CH areas and Intelligence reports on suspected trafficking activities. Workflow overview includes Data Collection, Threat Assessment & Alert Generation, Collaboration & Escalation, Investigation & Follow-Up, Investigation & Enforcement and Monitoring & Follow-up.</p>	<p>and validating the developed tools and the overall ENIGMA architecture against requirements, needs and technical constraints of target actors, as well as general and pilot specific indicators. Data collection and analysis will include 6-10 interviews with various actors per pilot. Pilot Case #1 & #2 will focus on the CH Stakeholders of the project only, whereas Pilot Case #3 on LEAs and Pilot Case #4 on all ENIGMA partners.</p>	<p>Recommendations (M32-M36, Lead: KEMEA), a set of policy recommendations for regional, national and EU policy makers and proposals for improvement and further steps will be developed. There is significant overlapping of task T6.1 with tools' development, integration and testing tasks in WP3, WP4, & WP5, since the task is initiated quite early (M17) in the project, to best serve this particular purpose. This will enable the Agile SDLC implementation and validation methodology to work out properly, especially by implementing and testing small chunks of software code or certain parts of the tool's functionality. The early engagement of the project's stakeholders will ensure the tools' adequate execution, by providing data and feedback (via scientific questionnaire and/or interview-based assessment) regarding the system and its functionalities. Further to the adoption of an Agile System/Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) framework, ENIGMA will undertake the " V-model" methodological approach for verification and validation. The Agile SDLC model complies with the ISO/IEC. 27001/2, ISO/IEC/IEEE</p>	<p>Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.13</p>	<p>AUTH, ECoE, UTU, NOE, ASOL and KIKLO</p>

<p>#4</p>	<p>Validation of Enigma decision support and data communications platform (KEMEA/HPOL) Pilot Case #4 will evaluate the integrated platform and how the individual components work together.</p>	<p>[a] Integration & testing of modules (AUTH), [b] ENIGMA Decision-Support Platform and Data/Communication Platform (CLK), [c] Public engagement tool (KMKG)</p>	<p>T5.1, T5.2, T 5.3</p>	<p>D5.1, D5.2, D5.3, D5.4, D5.5, D5.6</p>	<p>KEMEA, HPOL, KMKG, HM & all partners</p>	<p>Operational Scenario pertains to detailed narrative on the integration process of ENIGMA Platform tools and their functionalities for LEA CG identification, Decision-Support, Communication, and Data Management within ENIGMA and description of the Public Engagement Tool. HM Operational Scenario indicates that the National Heritage authority is alerted about an “authentic” artefact for sale in social media and intending to take the following steps: 1. Investigation, 2. Contacting the Seller, 3. Verification Process, 4. Legal, 5. Public Awareness, 6. Resolution.</p>	<p>15288:2015 and ISO/IEC TR 90005:2008 as well as ISO/IEC 12207:2008 and ISO/IEC 90003:2014 international standards.</p>	<p>Relevant KPI1.1, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.2, KPI1.4, KPI1.6, KPI1.7, KPI1.8, KPI1.9, KPI1.10, KPI1.11, KPI1.12, KPI1.18 Validation KPI2.1-2.12</p>	<p>All ENIGMA partners</p>
-----------	--	---	--------------------------	---	--	--	---	---	----------------------------

ANNEX II: FIGURINES AND OBJECTS REPLICAS FOR PILOT CASE 2 AND 4

1. Tête d'un homme-scorpion, élément architectural – inv.nr. 8918.00

Original: Near East Collection. O.04705

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Gozan, Tell Hafaf, North-Syria

Date: Iron Age, 9th c BC

Dimensions: 16 x 10 x 6.5 cm

Description: Head of a scorpion man (girtablilu), a hybrid creature known from the "Epic of Gilgamesh" with long beard and proto-ionic smile. The fragment originally belonged to the horseshoe-shaped pedestal of a half-column (or door-pillar?) of the "Scorpion Gate" in the palace of the capital of the Aramaic kingdom of Bēt Baḡyān. Like other sculptures, it was probably usurped by King Kapara. The existence of this fragment enabled our colleagues at the Vooraziatisch Museum in Berlin to restore the surviving fragments of a similar plinth that had been badly damaged by the bombing in 1943. E.G.

2. Masque : Akhénaton, pharaon égyptien – inv.nr. 8825.00

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Egypt

Date: 18th Dynasty

Dimensions: 17 x 13 cm

Description: N/A

3. Ushabti van Neferrenpet, de beheerder van de schatkist – inv.nr. 2496.00 (KMKG n° d'inv. E.05548)

Original: Egyptian Collection. E.05548

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Egypt

Date: New Kingdom, 19th Dynasty

Dimensions: 27 x 8 x 8 cm

Description: The ushabti of Neferrenpet, which dates from the Ramesside Period, was successively part of the collections of Anastasi, Raifé and de Meester de Ravestein. The latter, a collector of Egyptian antiquities, donated the ushabti to the Museum in 1884. The beautiful figurine can be distinguished by a curly hairstyle and a pleated dress with an impressive apron. The "overseer of the treasury." holds two attributes in his hand: the djed pillar and the knot of Isis (Tyet). His feet are finely sculpted and he is wearing sandals. Most of the hieroglyphic texts are inscribed on the back of the statue.

4. Statuette cycladique : femme assise – inv.nr. 8901.00 – avec patine

Original: Ancient Greek Collections, Inv. A.3029

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Amorgos, Greece

Date: 4th Millenium BC

Dimensions: 8 x 11 x 8 cm

Description: This sculpture shows a schematic representation of a seated woman. In the volume representing the head and neck, the nose and a finely engraved mouth stand out. The emphasis, however, is on the lower body with defined legs and pronounced buttocks. Characteristic of this exceptional statuette are the crossed legs, the extremely careful design, the attention to detail (fingers, knees, toes) and the harmonious balance of form. It may have been painted, but not the slightest trace of pigment remains. During the Neolithic period, human images were made everywhere in Greece. But the use of marble is very exceptional because it was very difficult to work due to the lack of metal tools. The meaning may perhaps be sought in the direction of fertility.

5. Herdenkingsscarabee van Amenhotep III – inv.nr. 8900

Original: Egyptian Collection. E.02368.

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Egypt

Date: Amenhotep III, New Kingdom

Dimensions: 16 x 10 x 6.5 cm

Description: This object belongs to the category of commemorative scarabs that king Amenhotep III produced on special occasions. They were intended for officials and are thus primarily instruments of royal propaganda. Five series are differentiated by the content of their texts. The Brussels scarab mentions lion hunts.

6. Paaseiland-beeldje Moai-hoofd reductie – inv.nr. 9523.00

Original: Moai Statue.
Location: KMKG
Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG
Origin: Easter Island, Chile
Date: s.d.
Dimensions: reduced scale
Description: N/A - No Image available.

7. Precolumbiaans offerbeeldje Chimù-cultuur (« gebroken oor ») – inv.nr. 8910.00

Original: Americas Collection, AAM 05713

Location: KMKG

Plaster Cast Workshop KMKG

Origin: Chimú Culture, Peru

Date: 1100-1450 AD

Dimensions: 16 x 10 x 6.5 cm

Description: Offering bearer : fetish depicted in "Tintin and the Broken Ear" by Hergé

ANNEX III: KMG'S CURRENT REGISTRATION AND DOCUMENTATION PROCEDURES

KMG maintains a digital inventory in their Collection Management System (CMS). The system is a tailored version of the MuseumPlus -suite by Zetcom (CH). A brief description of the current information documented in case an object is added to the KMG collections is presented below.

	Step	Description	Time consumption estimate (minutes)
1.	Provenance and authenticity research	When an object is offered to the museum a curator will research provenance and authenticity, using literature, on line resources like CH repositories and stolen CH goods databases to assess the authenticity and provenance. The least doubt should lead to a refusal of the offer.	30 - 60
2.	Entry of object in museum as part of the collection	A new acquisition arrives in the museum. It could be offered as a loan or gift, or an acquisition to fill gaps in the collection. Administrative formalities.	30
3.	Registration in the inventory	Initial identification consists of: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (new) Inventory number 2. object name 3. Collection name 4. Provenance/history 5. Acquisition As by law this inventory is handwritten, the books are not used later in workflow or activities.	15
4.	Creation of object-record in CMS	The information from the books is entered in the museum's Collection Management System (CMS). The initial record contains: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (new) Inventory number 2. object name 3. Collection name 4. Provenance/history 5. Acquisition 6. Location information of the object in the museum 7. Poss. IP of the creator or rights holder 	20
5.	Photography	The object is sent for photography, depending on the object, besides photography for	60

		registration purposes (including inv.nr and rulers on the image), publicity photos can be made	
6.	Ingest photos in DAM	The digital photos are entered into the Digital Asset Management System, DAM. Information entered: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Inventory number 2. Photographer name 3. Collection name 4. IP rights 	10
7.	Metadata exchange CMS - DAM	Low-res images are provided to CMS, information from DAM is copied to CMS vice versa	0
8.	Entry of additional object-background information by curator	Steps 1-7 describe initial registration. After that it is up to the curator what research is performed and what information is added to CMS. The procedures are not fixed, depending on factors like quality of the object, urgency, interest, capacity, cost. This is a continuous process. Categories are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Materials 2. Dimensions 3. Links to literature 4. Conservation and restauration information 5. Extensive provenance and historical research 	

Steps 1 -7 are executed in the period directly after the arrival of the object in the museum. The time needed for each step is relatively short, given that the information is at hand. Steps 1-7 take 120-180 minutes in total.

Photography including preparation takes 1 hour per object. **Step 8** is a continuous process after initial registration.

The data is stored in proprietary databases, **MuseumPlus** by **Zetcom** and **Mediahaven** by **Zeticon**, which can be accessed through API's. Currently, the **DAM** does not contain facilities for storage of 3D digital objects.

The screenshot shows the MuseumPlus interface for a record titled "E.432 Lamp (lighting device)". The interface is in Dutch and includes a search bar on the left with the query "e.432". Below the search bar, there are filters for "Domain Filter", "Saved Searches", and "Rangorde". The main content area is titled "Objecten (3)" and displays the following information:

- Model:** Standard
- Deelcollectie:** Egypte
- Inventarisnr.:** E.09751
- Objectnaam:** Lamp
- Titel:** Titel : ...
- Auteur/Cultuur:** (empty field)
- Datering:** Grieks-romeinse periode, -332 / 395
- Geo.ref.:** Plaats van herkomst : Onbekend
- Mat./Tech.:** Materiaal : Terracotta
- Afmetingen:** H x L x Ep : 5,6x 9 x 4,8 cm
- Huidige loc.:** Intern, Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis, Museum Kunst en Geschiedenis, Sector 1, Verdieping 4, 1.4.35 (reserve Egypte), Armoire à tiroirs B, lampes et ampoules, 3
- Perman. locat.:** (empty field)
- Locaties:** Intern, 20.10.2020, 1.4.35 (reserve Egypte), Armoire à tiroirs B, lampes et ampoules, 3 (Conservatie)

The interface also shows a navigation menu at the top with options like "Objecten", "Auteur/Cultuur", "Tentoonstelling", "Bruikleen en depot", "Bibliografie", "Adressen", "Conservatie", "Multimedia", and "Voorgaande module". The bottom of the screen features a navigation bar with a page indicator showing "1 / 3".

Figure 9 MuseumPlus record: E.432 Lamp (lighting device)

Objecten (1) ID: 85977 | adhoen 05/04/2023

Model: **Standard**

Deelcollectie: **Egypte** Andere nrs.

Inventarisnr.: **E.08670**

Objectnaam: **Vaatwerk**

Titel: **Titel : Geknikte pot met hoge hals en ringvormige basis**

Auteur/Cultuur: **Egyptisch**

Datering: **Onbekend** Geo.ref. Productieplaats : **Egypte**
Vindplaats : **Sediment (Onzeker, tombe 1053 (B.S.A.E. & E.R.A. 34-35))**

Domein: **Collectie Egypte**

Basisgegevens Verwerving/Waardebep. Aanvullende gegevens Beschrijving Classificaties Staat object Regie Referenties Administratieve gegevens

Mat./Tech. **Materiaal : Aardewerk (techniek)**

Afmetingen: **Afmetingen H x B x D : 15,5 x 1,0 cm**
Diameter : 10,0 cm

Beschr. lot: Aant. objecten

Huidige loc. **Intern, Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis, Museum Kunst en Geschiedenis, Sector 1, Verdieping 4, 1.4.35 (reserve Egypte), RES, Armoire céramique H, plateau 4**

Perman. local. **Intern, Koninklijke Musea voor Kunst en Geschiedenis, Museum Kunst en Geschiedenis, Sector 1, Verdieping 4, 1.4.35 (reserve Egypte), RES, Armoire céramique H, plateau 4**

Locaties: **Intern, 1.4.35 (reserve Egypte), RES, Armoire céramique H, plateau 4 (Conservatie)**

Figure 10 MuseumPlus record: E.08670 Vessel(container) Egyptian